

Recent conservation work in the hammer forge at Næs Ironworks Museum. Authentic fabric vs. function.

Stan Reed
Næs Ironworks Museum
Nesverkveien 240
4934 Nes Verk
Norway.
njm@jernverksmuseet.no/stanreed2@gmail.com
<http://www.jernverksmuseet.no>

Keywords: Næs Ironworks Museum, industrial heritage conservation, trip hammer, tail helve, belly helve.

Introduction.

The Norwegian Directorate for Cultural Heritage has initiated a conservation programme to rehabilitate fifteen prioritised industrial heritage sites to a level where they can be preserved through routine maintenance¹. Næs Ironworks is the best preserved of the old Norwegian ironworks and is one of the prioritised sites. Næs has received funding for project work on several of the historic buildings as part of this programme. Due to extensive deterioration of timbers in the hammer forge, the axles of the three water wheel driven trip hammers, one of the hammer hafts and other timber elements have been replaced. The hammer forge is one of three buildings at Næs protected under Norwegian cultural heritage legislation. This paper will present the project work done in the hammer forge and discuss some of the practical and theoretical challenges encountered.

Næs Ironworks Museum.

Næs Ironworks was founded in 1665 and was in production until 1959. The blast furnace was blown down in 1909. The last 50 years of production were based upon crucible steel, both cast and forged objects and steel bar. The surviving production buildings: a double charcoal blast furnace, hammer forge, crucible steelworks, machine workshop, a utility building housing remains of the works laboratory and a storage building, are either owned or managed by the museum. One of the workers cottages with an authentic interior and a house reserved for functionaries and their families are also owned by the museum. The blast furnaces, hammer forge and crucible steelworks are the only intact examples of such structures in Norway.

Production stopped in 1959 when a flood destroyed the works dam. Reconstructions of the main dam and a mill race, water wheel and bellows have been built to illustrate the concept of water power. The bellows are positioned as the original bellows were at the base of the blast furnace opening. A reconstruction of the furnace building has also been raised to protect the furnaces from the elements. Although this is primarily a protective structure, the building has the same form and dimensions as the furnace building from the middle of the 1800's giving an extra dimension to the museum's presentation of the furnaces. The water wheel and bellows are in operation during the summer months and are demonstrated by guides with every tour. These faithful copies give visitors first hand tangible experience of water power which aids understanding of the authentic machinery to be experienced in the forge and other buildings.

The Hammer Forge.

The surviving hammer forge at Næs houses three water wheel driven trip hammers, two belly helve and one tail helve. All three hammers were in use up until closure in 1959, but have not been in use for several decades. The forge is assumed to stand on the site of the original forge from 1665, but this is unconfirmed. The number of hammers and size of the first forge is unknown. At one point in the 1800's there appear to have been four hammers in the forge, the building being longer than it

was at the closure of the works. There was also another forge upstream from the main dam which housed two tail helve hammers. It is uncertain when the building was shortened, but two hammers appear to have been removed. The tail helve hammer being moved here from the other forge after that burnt in 1917. After the blast furnace was blown down in 1909 there was no longer a need for the Lancashire hearths for fining, these were also removed.

All three hammers are operated by axles directly connected to their water wheels. The wheel spokes are of oak, the wheels have an iron rim with a diameter of 3.4 – 3.8m, and width of c. 1.5m. The axles are c. 8.6m long, square in cross section, c. 0.8m x 0.8m, and consist of nine pine logs bound together by iron bands. The older bands are forge welded as whole squares and driven into place. These have been replaced in the central part of the axles of the two belly helve hammers with two-part bands bolted together. Whole bands were still used at both ends to hold the gudgeons in place. The gudgeons are solid iron blocks, square at one end, circular at the other. The square section is inserted into the axle and is slightly pyramidal, narrowing towards the bearing end. The central pine log is shorter to accommodate the gudgeons. These are wedged into place with wedges between the gudgeon and the eight timbers. The timber is then expanded against the gudgeon and iron bands by driving wedges into the logs. A starting hole is worked in the timber with an iron wedge and the wooden wedge inserted into the hole. The wedges are approximately the length of the gudgeon inside the axle – c. 0.6m and were traditionally driven in with an iron tipped beam hung from the rafters. The water wheels and cam rings are wedged onto the axle using folded wedging. The hammer hafts are c. 3.5m long, the hammer heads vary in size. The hammers assembly, especially the belly helve hammers closely follow the instructions in Sven Rinman's *Bergwerks Lexicon* of 1789ⁱⁱ. The hurst frames in Rinmans illustration are of wood, whereas the frames of the hammers at Næs are of cast iron. The hammer hafts at Næs are of birch and there is a verbal tradition that they should be of a birch log with a large number of knots. These presumably give the haft a form of internal reinforcement better enabling them to withstand the stresses they are placed under.

Fig. 1. Rinman's illustration of a belly helve hammer.

Fig. 2. The largest belly helve hammer at Næs.

The building collapsed in 1966 after a heavy snowfall. A replacement building, mirroring the one that collapsed in size and form, was completed in 1969. The hammers and other fast inventory appear to have been largely undamaged by the collapse and were given protected status under Norwegian cultural heritage legislation after the collapse, in 1967. The roof tiles in the forge rested on battens with no underlay allowing fumes from the coke furnaces to exit through the roof, see fig 3. After production stopped the building was no longer heated or maintained, rain and melting snow presumably leaked into the building through the gaps between the tiles causing significant rot damage to the structure.

Fig. 3. Fumes from the coke furnace exit through the roof, 1956. Photo: Karsten Ellefsen.

Substantial restoration work was undertaken on the foundations of all three hammers in the 1980's to address subsidence caused by rotting foundations. Each axle and water wheel was lifted and the timber foundations replaced with gravel with a layer of creosote impregnated telegraph poles lain on top. Short sections of interlaced telegraph poles closed the foundations towards the wheel pit holding the gravel in place. New wedges were driven in at the ends of the axles to strengthen the wedging of the gudgeons. It's clear from the pattern of wedging and the dimensions used that the ends of axles were in a state of deterioration when this work was carried out. Other than this no interventions appear to have been made to the hammers or water wheels.

The forge was the subject of analysis in 2002/3 by Christian Bode as part of his studies at HTW University of Applied Sciences, Berlinⁱⁱⁱ. He produced a condition report, analysis of fungal and insect attack and carried out resistance drilling to document the condition of the timbers in the largest hammer. He also replaced the base of one of the earthfast posts and as a theoretical exercise analysed the climate in the building, suggesting the interventions and dehumidification equipment which would be necessary to create a climate that could secure in-situ preservation of the timber.

Dating of the fabric.

The restoration work from the 1980's could be read from the apparent difference in age of the materials, but dating the authentic elements of the hammers has proved challenging. The hammers' assembly closely follow the instructions in Rinman's Bergwerks Lexicon but there are no grounds for assuming that the surviving elements date to the late 1700's. The only datable elements were the hammer hafts. Partially legible dates from the 1950's were carved into the end of each hammer shaft. Presumably indicating the date the shafts were installed. Despite only being in use for a maximum of 8 years a new haft for the tail helve hammer stood in the forge ready for installation.

A photo from 1948 shows the iron bands binding the axle timbers on the largest hammer are different from those present on the axle today. The whole rings having been replaced with two part rings and bolts. These were presumably replaced during dismantling and renewal of the axle timbers. This indicates that the timbers in the axle of large hammer were replaced in 1948 or later

and in use for a maximum of 12 years. There is verbal evidence for shifting of the timber posts of the largest hammer in the 1950's. The works is also known to have had a store of seasoned timber ready to replace the machine parts when necessary. There is also verbal evidence that two of the hammer heads were recast in the 1930's.

There are very few photos of production in the forge despite production continuing in to the 1950's and no other available evidence to indicate an age for the various machine parts. It seems likely however that those subjected to the most stress under use were changed relatively often. An indication of the stresses involved can be found in Rinman's description of the axle^{iv}. He recommends using at least four pine logs bound together, as attempts to use a single pine trunk lasted no more than 6 months before it was twisted asunder. We have estimated a lifespan of c. 20 years for the timbers in the axle, but this is no more than an educated guess. The lifespan of the machine parts will presumably have varied considerably depending on how intensely they were used. The timber in the structures over the belly helve hammers and the cast iron hurst frames are probably the oldest elements. The forge was in active use up until 1959 and underwent several structural changes in the 1900's. Several of the individual elements in the hammer assemblies were presumably replaced several times during the 1900's. The timbers in the axle of the large hammer, which is the subject of further discussion later in this article, were in use for 12 of the hammer forge's 294 years of production.

Condition of the timbers.

The new building constructed in 1969 used impregnated timber posts and glued laminated roof trusses. The exterior has vertical weatherboarding, with gaps between the boards along the west wall that faces the river. A reconstruction of the mill race has also been built, but only alongside the building. It is not connected to the dam. Whereas the water wheels and mill race were originally separated from the hammers by an internal wall, both are now visible from within the building to aid understanding for visitors. There are louvre window openings along the opposite wall and irregular openings where the construction and weatherboarding are adapted to the terrain. The building is very open and the internal climate follows to a large degree the external climate. The building has a large internal space 22m x 14,5m, 8m to the roof. The internal climate is relatively slow to adjust however and with changes in the weather moisture condenses on the iron.

There is also a spring that runs approximately 1m under the earth floor, running out in one of the wheel pits and out into the river. Two of the wheel pits had standing water in them all year round. The opening out to the river has now been cleared so that any water that comes in runs out when river levels drop. Drainage pipes, laid in gravel with a layer of heavy duty plastic over them, channel the water from the spring out into the river. The plastic, which is disguised by a further layer of gravel, prevents evaporation into the building.

Relative humidity (RH) in the building is high. Measurement of the temperature and RH levels together with selective analysis of fungal and insect activity carried out by Mycoteam suggested that RH levels were not high enough to sustain rot or insect attacks in fresh timber, but that periodic fungal activity in already weakened timber with dormant spores could be activated by high RH levels or other wetting^v. This periodic activity would over a long period of time cause further deterioration. The starting point for the fungal and insect activity that could be registered in the timber was assumed to have started some time ago, either as a result of exposure to rain and snow after production stopped and/or subsequent roof leaks. Dataloggers have recently been installed in the forge and other buildings. Preliminary results show a high RH, fluctuating between 45 and 100 % during the latter half of the winter and spring of 2015. The newly replaced birch hammer haft for the tail helve hammer has fungal growth visible on its surface, identified as *Cylindrobasidium evolvens*. This was first noticed the winter after installation. The laboratory that carried out analysis of the growth, Mycoteam, concluded that the timber was infected prior to

installation and that the timber may not have been sufficiently dry before installation. The fungal attack died out naturally during the summer. No action was therefore taken. It returned however the following winter when RH levels increased. During the winter months, most of the timber in the forge, both new and old timber in the hammers and that of the building construction, showed moisture levels of around 20%, measured both on the surface and at a depth of 5cm. This is of course the critical level for fungal growth. The fungal growth on the new hammer haft and the moisture level measurements in the timber strongly support the initial conclusion that periodic fungal growth following high RH levels could have caused the continued deterioration of the timbers. There have been leaks through the roof along the mill race where the building is partially open. These leaks will have contributed to wetting at selected points and therefore to continued fungal activity, but cannot be responsible for activity at other points along the axles.

The timber in the axles could appear to be solid on the surface at one point, but severely weakened by rot at other points along their length. The rot attack was most apparent at either end of the axles where the iron bands were placed tightly together to hold the gudgeons in place, and appeared to be more acute in the centre of the axle than on the surface. The iron in the forge is often visibly wet from condensation when the weather changes. It is possible that where the iron bands are closely placed condensation has contributed to wetting of the timber and also prohibited drying.

Christian Bode's resistance drilling clearly shows the decay concentrated at either end, but also spread irregularly along the length of the axle, see fig. 4. It also shows that all the timbers are affected, but that where one is rotten the others may be in reasonable condition, whereas further along the axle the rot is concentrated in another of the timbers. The first step in the conservation work was cutting the timbers to remove them. These randomly placed cross sections through the axles confirm the situation recorded by Bode's drilling, see fig. 5. All three axles were in a similar condition. Whereas the positioning of the iron bands may in part explain the concentration of decay at the ends, the apparently random pattern of decay along the central part of the axles is difficult to explain.

Fig. 4. Resistance drilling cross sections through the axle of the large belly helve hammer in 2002. Red indicates rot. Both sections show the same results. The upper set is exploded to ease reading. From Bode 2002/3.

Figs. 5 + 6. Random cross section through the axle and wedging of the gudgeon from the 1980's in the largest belly helve hammer.

The aim of the restoration work in the 1980's was to redress subsidence caused by rotting foundations. The work was successful, but funding didn't cover provision for work on the rot in the axles. The gudgeons were simply wedged tight with large wedges. These are clearly distinguishable for the original wedges. Further decay was clearly visible in the axle ends, the gudgeons have loosened again and many of the iron bands hung loose. At the water wheel end of the tail helve hammer the gudgeon had loosened completely, the axle no longer carried the wheel which had slumped, coming to rest in the base of the wheel pit, see fig. 7. All three axles were subsequently supported along their lengths with wooden blocks and iron bars taking the weight. If the axles hadn't been supported in this way the other gudgeons would have loosened under the weight of the water wheels and cam rings, and the machinery would have collapsed. The timbers in the axles were so weakened that they could no longer be bound together to function as a load bearing unit.

Fig. 7. The gudgeon in the tail helve hammer's axle had loosened and the water wheel rested in the wheel pit.

The hammer haft of the tail helve hammer was also severely damaged by rot and insect attack. The central part was rotten almost through the timber. It was successfully removed in one piece, but fell apart during an attempt to move it out of the building. The base of the earthfast posts of both belly helve hammers were also severely damaged by rot. Mycoteams analysis of some of the fungal growths identified honey fungus (*Armillaria mellea*) growing in one of the rotten posts. This is a fungus normally associated with wet wood on forest floors. The spring running under the floor holds moisture levels in the ground constantly high and timber in contact with the ground is likely to rot. All wood has been removed from the floor, except the earthfast posts, to prevent fungal growth. Fungus can sometimes be seen to grow on the earth floor. Sawdust and small woodchips from working of the axle timbers caused new growth, despite rigorous attempts to clear the debris. Openings in the roof and more louvre windows in both gable ends are planned as a first attempt to improve air circulation to reduce condensation and aid moisture transportation. Further alterations may be necessary if these are not successful.

Conservation work.

A local firm, Boylestad og Moen DA, who have a lot of experience rehabilitating historical buildings carried out the practical work in co-operation with the museum. The museum undertook conservation of the iron elements. The hammers were documented prior to dismantling both by the museum's curator and the craftsmen undertaking the work. Investigations into preserved hammers elsewhere showed significant variation in the details of the machinery and how they are assembled. It was therefore considered especially important to re-assemble the machinery following the local traditions. Wedging was identified as a key element in the construction. This is a method of connecting machinery that none of the people involved in the work had direct experience of. It was of particular importance to be able to document the wedging to gain as much insight as possible as to how the gudgeons were wedged in place to support the functioning machinery. It was of course a goal to create an authentic as possible situation, but was also necessary to wedge in such a way that the gudgeon and axle were able to carry the weights placed upon them.

The water wheels and cam rings were suspended from temporary frames built around the hammers and the axle was supported on wooden blocks. Once the machinery was supported the timbers in the axles were cut up. The timber was so deteriorated that there was nothing to be gained from attempting to dismantle the timbers whole. Sample sections have been retained by the museum for reference. The water wheels remained in place during the whole operation. The hammer hafts of the belly helve hammers also remained in place, but the whole assembly of the tail helve hammer was dismantled. All the moveable iron objects were removed from the building and steam cleaned. This process removed mechanically all dirt and surface rust. The iron was oiled with penetrating, rust inhibiting oil – Owatrol. The upper layer of creosote impregnated posts were removed and replaced with pine logs with a high degree of heartwood.

Fig. 8. Tail helve hammer partially dismantled.

Fig. 9. Steam cleaning.

The axle timbers were also of heart pine, seasoned over several years. Twelve or thirteen logs were cut for each axle and the most suitable nine selected. The original axles consisted of a combination of square sawn logs mixed with logs with part of their original waney edge. This combination was retained. The logs were roughly cut to size away from site and worked in-situ by hand with axe and draw knife. The iron bands were refitted in the same positions as they had on the original axles. These were driven in from the ends and had to fit tightly over the logs. The timber had to be adjusted to allow the bands to be driven into position.

Two of the axle ends could be removed from the building whole, allowing them to be dismantled piece by piece to document in more detail the methods of wedging the gudgeons in place. The original wedging was also observed in-situ, but only in the ends of the axles. The pattern of wedging showed some similarities and differences for all three hammers. There is a verbal tradition at Næs that additional wedges were inserted relatively often to hold the axles tight during use. The differences observed are assumed to be a result of the differential need for additional wedging. For all three hammers the original wedging appeared to be concentrated around the gudgeons, on all four sides in a rough ring or square with rounded off corners. Wedges were driven into one another in this area, whereas the area furthest from the gudgeon was, as a rule, free from wedges. Many of the wedges were in poor condition and it was difficult to determine their original dimensions. Those that appeared to be intact were c. 0.6m in length, the same length as the gudgeon within the axle. They may have been of varying wood types, some were clearly pine. Wedges of the same dimensions were used in the rebuild. Hand working them would have been prohibitively time consuming and pine sawn to size was used. In the state they were recovered in, the originals appeared to be more rounded in cross section.

Fig.10. Recording of the wedging of the gudgeon in the axle end. Wedges from the 1980's directly over the gudgeon.

Fig. 13. Reassembling the axle.

Fig. 14. Driving the iron bands onto the axle.

Fig. 11. Original and new wedges.

Fig. 12. Driving in new wedges.

Driving in wedges around the gudgeon, c. 0.10m in from the edge of the logs as the originals were, caused the logs to partially split. Similar splitting was observed in the original logs. Extra wedges were needed not only to bring the logs and gudgeons together, but also to fill the splits and cracks that opened up. Wedging in a closed ring or square around the gudgeon was the simplest way of avoiding openings in the timber. It is possible that splitting would have been less prominent if the wedges had been more rounded or a different technique used to open up the timber prior to driving in. Single wedges were observed in some places in the original axles. How these were driven in without causing splitting is unclear. It was not necessary for us to wedge outside of the area around the gudgeon to bring the components together, with one exception, so it was not attempted for fear of causing more splitting in the timbers.

Iron wedges were also used in the original hammer assemblies. They are present in the ends of the hammer hafts along with wooden wedges, wedging the hurst and shaft together, and used for both belly helve hammers between the iron bands and cam rings, driven in between folded wedges. Iron wedges were also used in the end of the axle of the tail helve hammer. They were not re-used in the tail helve or smallest belly helve hammer, but were in the largest hammer as a condition of the permission to carry out the work. More consideration should have been given to re-use of the iron wedges in the other two hammers, but the possibility of driving these in at a later date remains. They were driven in between the iron band and cam ring on the largest hammer after the gudgeon was wedged in placed. This caused pressure on the iron bands which was transferred to the timbers pressing them apart. These gaps needed to be closed to prevent moisture entering the axle. No observations of wedging between the timbers were made in any of the three hammers. Filling these openings with wedges was therefore considered a poor solution. A second ring of wedges was driven in between the first set and the iron bands, pressing the timbers together again. A second

complete ring of wedges in this position was not observed in the original axle, but was considered an acceptable solution, and possibly one which may, under similar circumstances, have been chosen by the blacksmiths. It is interesting to note that for the first hammer we followed the original wedging as closely as possible, stopping when the gudgeon was tight, but by the third hammer the craftsmen doing the wedging had a good enough understanding of the processes to suggest this solution. Once the second ring of wedges was driven in the axle was extremely tight and would not receive more wedges.

All three axles were successfully wedged together and the wheels wedged on them. The process of wedging followed as closely as we could determine it the authentic pattern of wedging used by the blacksmiths, with the exception of one end of the axle of the largest belly helve hammer where a problem had to be solved and function prioritised. The experience gained made it clear that exactly replicating the original patterning of wedging, which was a result of repeated tightening of the axle after periods of use, would have been impossible with fresh, unused timbers. It is possible that the iron wedges between the iron bands and cam rings may also have been a secondary addition.

Authentic fabric vs. functionality.

The hammers, along with the crucible steelworks, storage building and an area around them were the subject of a protection order after the collapse of the forge. They are protected under paragraph 15 of the Norwegian Cultural Heritage Act^{vi}. Exemption from the act has to be obtained before major changes can be undertaken. There were several on-site meetings with the authorities to discuss the appropriate interventions prior to our applying for exemption. Splicing the timbers in the axles was discussed. Whilst splicing is used successfully as a means of preserving sections of authentic fabric in deteriorated log buildings it would have been, in our opinion, an unhistorical method of treating a machine part. The pattern of rot damage also appeared to exclude this as a practical possibility. In addition if the timbers were to be load bearing, carrying the water wheels and cam rings, they would have needed to have been supported under each splice. The only realistic alternative appeared to us to be replacing the timbers in the axles in their entirety. This would entail a loss of authentic fabric, but the machine part, consisting not just of the timbers, but also the authentic iron bands and gudgeons would regain its functionality and be a load bearing element once again.

The tail helve hammer was in critical condition. We wished to begin with this hammer to gain experience of the processes and review the results before finally deciding on a course of action for the other two hammers. Permission was obtained for replacing the timbers in the tail helve hammer axle and for installing a new hammer haft. The work was completed successfully. Both the water wheel and cam ring hung on the axle, which can be turned by hand as part of a maintenance strategy.

The hammer regained its functionality, but there was no attempt made to restore it to a functional state. The regional authorities wished for clarification of this issue prior to considering our application. We chose not to focus on restoration at this time; the strategy for the interventions was preserving the machinery. If the hammer were to be fully restored we would have to learn to use it by trial and error, experimenting with a unique cultural heritage object. The foundations have been changed, the timber being replaced by gravel. The potential effect of this on the hammer's stability is unknown. The mill race could be rebuilt to run the wheel, but one of the project's goals was to reduce moisture levels in the building because of the detrimental effects on the remaining authentic timbers. A sprinkler system was recently installed to protect against the potentially devastating effects of a fire. Restoring the furnaces to heat up iron for forging would also pose challenges. The number of visitors who could safely view the hammer and furnace would be limited in relation to the potential interest. None of these challenges are insurmountable, but the museum decided to explore the possibilities of building a working copy. We have positive experience of the copies of

the water wheel and bellows. A hammer copy could be sited more favourably for viewing and could be used freely without any concern for damaging a unique cultural object. Building a hammer copy is a priority, but work has not yet started in earnest. A number of parameters, e.g. which type of hammer, its dimensions, whether it will be run by guides as part of every tour, simply demonstrating the mechanics of a functioning hammer or whether it will be integrated into a viewing forge operated by a working blacksmith demonstrating not just the mechanics but also the skills needed to operate it, are yet to be determined.

In reviewing the work with the tail helve hammer the regional authorities requested that we considered the possibility of preserving one of the hammers as is. The museum concluded however that replacing the timbers in the axles of both the belly helve hammers and splicing the base of the earthfast posts with new heart pine, separating the timber from the waterlogged soil with gravel, was the best way to secure long term preservation of the machinery as a whole. Permission was given to splice new material in the timbers in contact with the ground for both hammers and to replace the axle timbers of the smallest belly helve hammer, but the regional authority maintained that the axle of the largest hammer could, and therefore should, be preserved in-situ. This decision was challenged and decided at appeal by the Directorate for Cultural Heritage in the museum's favour.

Our contention was that deterioration of the timbers had reached a similar stage in both hammer axles and that preservation of them in their present condition was not feasible. The interventions that would be necessary to seriously attempt long term preservation would include changes to the buildings structure to close it to the elements and installation of dehumidification equipment. We considered these to be unacceptable alterations to the building's character. The forge is an open, earth floored, damp, industrial locality and preservation strategies should consider the limitations this places on in-situ conservation. Even though replacing the timbers entailed an irreversible intervention in authentic fabric, we considered the machinery's functionality to be of more importance. The value of these unique machines lay not in the patina of the logs in the axle, but in the function of the whole.

The water wheels and cam rings are carried by the axle and it's functionality as a load bearing element was not just a theoretical consideration. Preservation of the whole was, in part, dependant on a functioning axle to bear their weight. Without this the axle timbers, water wheels and cam rings would also have to be supported by cradles or shoring, impairing appreciation of the machinery. Unable to ensure preservation of the timbers we considered their replacement inevitable and foresaw a situation where their condition would eventually deteriorate to the extent that part of the hammer forge would have to be closed to the public for security reasons. Eventual collapse of the axles would also risk damaging the other elements of the hammers.

The problem for us was not just whether preservation of the timbers in situ was a realistic possibility, but also whether they, in their deteriorated state, should be prioritised. In our opinion the loss of cultural historical value from the proposed replacement of authentic fabric was a lesser evil than the loss of value to the hammer by preserving the axle as it was in its non functional state, retaining the incorrect wedging from the 1980's and supporting the axle, water wheels and cam rings to prevent collapse. Central to this train of thought is the appreciation of function as a bearer of meaning and value in industrial heritage. Preservation of authentic fabric is a given in cultural heritage, and is embedded in legislation and guidelines. It was difficult to find similar support for the consideration of function in the available guidelines and literature. Preservation of authentic fabric is undoubtedly an important premise for limiting destructive interventions, but in the author's opinion this case illustrates that one should also be open to considering other factors when assigning value.

Fig. 15. Tail helve hammer before conservation. It was reassembled incorrectly in the 1980's with the tail down and the head on the anvil. The water wheel, cam ring and part of the axle rested on the ground. The balance ring at the end was supported on blocks concealed behind the bearing.

Fig. 16. Tail helve hammer after conservation.

ⁱ <http://www.riksantikvaren.no/Tema/Tekniske-og-industrielle-kulturminner>. Accessed 06/08/2015.

ⁱⁱ <http://www.jernkontoret.se/en/about-us/library/bergverkslexicon/>. See Hammarställning and Stångjärnshammare, and http://admin.jernkontoret.se/om_oss/vart_bibliotek/bergverkslexicon/TabXVII_fig1.jpg. Accessed 06/08/2015.

ⁱⁱⁱ Bode, C. 2002/3. Die Hammerschmiede des Næs Jernverksmuseums in Südnorwegen. Diplomarbeit vorgelegt dem Fachbereich 5, Gestaltung Studiengang Restaurierung/Grabungstechnik der Fachhochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin. See <http://www.bode-restaurierung.de/43314.html> for pdf files. Accessed 06/08/2015.

^{iv} <http://www.jernkontoret.se/en/about-us/library/bergverkslexicon/>. See Hammarhjulstock. Accessed 06/08/2015.

^v Mattsson, J. 2011. Næs Jernverksmuseum – vurdering av fukt-, sopp- og insektskader i hammerbygningen. Unpublished Mycoteam report, project no. 201110101.

^{vi} <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/cultural-heritage-act/id173106/>. Accessed 06/08/2015.